

WCIA MayDay Archiveathon

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In this blog, Dr Abi Glen from the OHOS Archives Lab at the University of Glasgow discusses the project's collaboration with the Welsh Commission for International Affairs.

It feels fitting that a Temple of Peace and Health should be so...peaceful. Craig Owen, the [Welsh Commission for International Affairs \(WCIA\)](#) Heritage Advisor, led a tour of the building. He elaborated on its rich history as a repository of materials relating to WCIA's instrumental role on post-WWI peace-keeping efforts and human rights frameworks (and as a film set for [Doctor Who](#)).

To Peace or not to Peace.

My time with Craig was spent not only learning about the wealth of heritage work at the Temple, but running an Archiveathon with a group of student volunteers. The collaboration is intended as a stepping stone towards building capacity for *online* public access to peace archives, and *onsite* volunteering and heritage work at the Temple of Peace. Craig and his team are concerned with the digital future of [WCIA's Peace Archives](#), and are linking with OHOS with the aim of making the archives and catalogues available now, and fifty years hence.

The Peace Archives are also fascinating as they provide a case study in a devolved context (with Welsh, UK and International user audiences) of how community organisations can use digital developments to safeguard and preserve their heritage resources for access by future generations. Through Craig's masterplan of partnership working, community engagement and focused volunteer participation, we can see best practice tools for community heritage providers in working towards everything from digital preservation, to building national collections.

One of the main focuses of the workshop was on "Hidden Histories"; a long-running project encompassing wide-ranging research undertaken by [Wales For Peace](#) volunteers, partners, community groups, students and academics – with 'new histories' added as further stories are unearthed by current volunteers working from the Temple's archives and collections. Each 'Hidden History' is published on the [WCIA website](#), where each article links to digitised resources and source materials for further research and study.

Staff and participants continue to work together on digital preservation, redesign, and repackaging of Hidden Histories and their supporting archival base. Craig's charm and commitment was in full evidence as he had gathered everyone from trustees of the Friends of the Temple of Peace, to undergrads from local universities on placement, to MPhil mature students broadening their research. Also remarkable was the sheer range of supporting documents and reference guides to support those on placements, as well as careful spread of resourcing so that the students have face-to-face interaction.

Let it not be said heritage workers don't have fun

A very great thanks to all of the student participants who made the workshop possible, and of course to Craig for his endless commitment, humour, and enthusiasm for the project.

Craig casually using The Force.

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